

Strained remodeled bone model, an introductory numerical model of bone to explain orthodontic movement and relapse. Hundren theory modeled via a Mohammed body

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Abstract

There are many theories about orthodontic movements that is resulted from application of the well orthodontic force during orthodontic treatment. We want to introduce a new theory explaining the basis of the orthodontic movement. We had called it (Hundren theory) in the name of the Kurdish maxillofacial surgeon (Hundren Mohammed Ali). It is valid to represent orthodontic movement and directed to explain the relapse after treatment. Mohammed bodies are the numerical models that had built by the main author to represent he living structures. The current paper outline the needed biomechanical explanation of the current suggested theory.

Keywords: Bone remodeling, Biomechanics, orthodontics, relapse, numerical simulation surgery, Orthopedics, Frontal bone, Compliant mechanism

Introduction

The bone in many instances represented as solid continuous mass. Bone is a laminated composite with complex orthotropicity that is gaping across the different side to impart the needed mechanical stress holder with at least biphasic properties. Its elasticity, plasticity, viscoelasticity, viscoelasticity and vesicoelastoplasticity is remarkable. All of these phases are meeting in the same structure. Dental alignment is of paramount importance for many aspects of the life. Current theories lacking many important aspects and mechanical basis to be accepted as a scientific fact. (1)

Orthodontic movement model (Hundren theory)

The craniofacial growth had multiple connections with orthodontics in the early stages of growth, but pure dental alignment after skeletal maturity had little or even no connection to craniofacial growth. Theories that explain orthodontic movement are highly erroneous and based upon many orthodontists` opinions without any consideration of the nature of the bone itself or biomechanics as they claim. Two main highly defective theories had been proposed in this subject. Both are highly biased.

- 1- Theory that describes the piezoelectric effect upon the bone remodeling which had no biological evidence, apart from pure theoretical assumption. The role of the calcium salts in the structure of the

bone is to stabilize the collagen fibers on a very small scale and restrict its sliding over each other (2). It is not valid to explain the relapse occurring after an orthodontic treatment course. No valid well controlled experimental setting had shown the validity of this theory (3). This suggestion of response of the piezoelectric stimulation of the hydroxyapatite crystals without demonstrating single evidence support this assumption. **We should emphasize upon the fact that the bone is composite inside composite.**

- 2- Bone remodeling theory where they say that there's bone resorption in regions of the compression and bone apposition in the regions of the tension also is an imaginary description. It regards the bone as plastic and also does not stand for explaining the relapse after the treatment. Its core neglects the fact that the bone is composite in nature and has multiple interacting phases viscous, elastic and plastic.

In the case of the mandible the collagen fibers are continuous from the right condyle to the left one

Figure 1 osteocytes is mechanical strain gauge, strain presenting cell, act like ant where they but they are tiny blind individuals

Bone is not solid homogeneous material. Bone orthotropicity is derived and controlled by global loads and local loads, as well as the different cortical and medullary regions. In composite signs we could regard the bone as shell as an analogue for the cortical portion and infill as analogue for the medullary part. They are interacting in between to resist orthodontic movement. No marked bone remodeling will start unless marked movement which will be resulted from the highest strain of elastic components. This second more widely accepted theory is the assumption of reciprocating bone resorption and a position at alternative sites, which is not standing to explain the relapse that resulted after removal of orthodontics treatments hardware. Many orthodontists' last resort is to depend upon long term retention devices to escape relapse.

Figure 2 Bone structure is very complex and related mainly to the mechanical load

Relapse's root is residing in the complex orthotropicity of the bone fibers and residual strain persist after finishing of the orthodontic treatment rather than from the occlusion. Occlusion had little effect on the position of the teeth

Orthodontics as a science is observational steps with myriad tools and equipment, where orthodontists do their jobs without clear cut knowledge about the basis of orthodontic movements, but rather a good amount of certainty of the results depending on the long history of predictable response of the dentition to the well-controlled forces.

Figure 3 Trabecular orientation is determined in the first order by the global stiffness then by the local need

One Of important aspects that need special attention is that we are regarding the loads on the jaws is one of the prime affecters upon the movements of the teeth. When a force is applied on a segment of the dentition other regions will be affected also via transition of the loads. The presence of the teeth in the jaws provide great weakeners that should be respected by the biomechanical researchers. Deformity will result in more accelerated

orthodontic movement. It is senseless to do orthodontic treatment on patients with brain death (an example of a patient who cannot use his jaws), because orthodontic movement is just for healthy patients with functional jaws. In another word all orthodontic patients had a certain amount of jaw deformation caused by activities such as mastication and chewing where all teeth were affected by all as well as themselves. It is futile to try orthodontic movement for a patient who can't move his jaws.

Major of the force that align the teeth is coming from the passive effect of jaws deformation on the teeth where these are not loaded

Relapse after orthodontics treatment and its explanation will provide the best explanation of the orthodontic movement itself. We assume that the cause for relapse is that : there is no robust bone material that has been formed to hold the dentition in its new configuration after completion of the treatment, and removal of the orthodontic device, is the main cause of relapse. During orthodontics treatment there will be stretching and straining of the most pliable least stiff component of the stomatognathic system, namely PD ligaments and adjacent parts of the bone. These tissues have the least ability to change their surroundings in the direction away from the roots. Post extraction movement of the teeth in the vicinity (overeruption of the opposing teeth and inclination of the adjacent teeth) could take decades to be established, clearly showing this point of how living systems could take a long time to produce iatrogenic orthodontic movement. In contrast to that, bone pathologies that cause displacement of the teeth into a new position will have no return to the pre-displacement alignment after management of the pathology due to 2 reasons (4).

- 1- This movement had been started from the most stable portion with highest stiffness to least stiff portion.
- 2- The molecular biology of most cysts and tumors of the jaws cause potent bone displacement. This had been clearly shown in the regional acceleratory phenomenon

Many pathological conditions that produce dental malalignment because they affect bone organization. They are starting, in most of this condition, from the stiffest area (bone) to the area with least stiffness (PD ligament region). In such a case, no straining is happening and we are starting from the bone remodeling in the first place. Pathological conditions also had a very powerful molecular biologically based arm.

Orthodontic movement is initiated by straining of the periodontium. After a certain limit of this strain, the bone surrounding this highly strained region begins to remodel, but a certain amount of tissues remains strained.

Relapse is simple returns of the tissue to its original status. The resultant relapse is depending on the balance between the straining formed and degree of remodeling and the changes occurred due to growth potential. The changes could be growth restraining or increase in a certain direction. **After removal of the orthodontic hardware the strained tissues will start immediately to do opposite uncontrolled orthodontic movement, where this is the definition of relapse**

Relapse is a summation of return from this straining and the net result from bone remodeling. With aging maturation of osseous collagen fibers will result in highly organized fibers and stiffer regions. This will necessitate higher strain to reach the threshold of remodeling. This will bring more drastic changes of the roots seen as resorption and relapse will be higher in most of these instances. Root resorption typically due to more aggressive remodeling. The center of the rotation due to lateral load is much lower than that of a well-osseointegrated implant.

Many of the orthodontists' witnessed by the author had little knowledge about biomechanics. Actually, many orthodontics are just users of tools that were advanced in the manufacturing capability that had enabled them to apply different forces, vectors and magnitudes.

Orthodontics models

Orthodontic movement are capable of producing change in the bone shape and the ability to transfer the tooth within the bone structure due to 2 causes

- Presence the ability to introduce reciprocal movement that should be understood in the context of ability of the jaws to be deformed globally and the tooth socket are one of the most affected regions by this global deformation whether it is affected directly by the same tooth or other tooth anywhere. This had been shown clearly in our paper about passive effect of the jaws deformation on the dental socket. (5) Reciprocal movement is a prerequisite for any growth in the skeletal tissues (6)
- The nature of the PD ligament region itself in the region directly affected by the orthodontics forces. The high vascular content, excellent perfusion, their resilience, high cellular turnover of the calcified tissues and capability of molecular pathways to be recalled by the PD tissues. PD tissues had high uptake of bisphosphonate when administered

Many components are investing the root inside the alveolar process. Mechanical response of the tooth to the loads are extremely difficult to characterize, but a certain level of certainty has been achieved. Teeth could sustain movement (displacement inclination rotation ...etc.) in many instances. The controlled planned movement is done in the orthodontic movement. The movement in many cases will be followed by the return of the teeth to their original shape. This return, which had been widely accepted to be called relapse, could assume many pictures.

In contrast to pure dental orthodontic treatment, relapse after orthognathic surgery is under the category of the process we witness in the case of distraction osteogenesis, while relapse after orthodontic treatment is totally different in which the biphasic stomatognathic response should be considered. In more precise description: bone geometric and material itself nonlinearity is beyond the scope of this text. In many times what seems to be stable results after orthognathic surgery and we think that solid bone had been formed at the cutting site, actually the bony interfaces of bone cut during orthognathic surgery could remain fibrous where relapse will form. Intraosseous fibrosis at the site of osteotomies in the case of orthognathic surgery is a well-recognized entity. This has been witnessed many times by the main author. These tissues had the ability to be mobilized and deformed. They have potential for regaining their original position that could resemble slow distraction osteogenesis. The speed of relapse is a subject of debate in the orthognathic surgery specialty. Here, we present many models representing digital models of the orthodontic movement. These are the main models

- One model we had represented 2 elements.
 - o one layered in successive regions
 - o another radial component from the tooth
- Second is a layered model with successive plastic and elastic layers.

Verification of the numerical models should be done via results of the orthodontic treatment done on real patients. Digital models could be different substantially from living models in structures and boundary conditions, but it is acceptable if they yield similar results. Validation by comparing natural and virtual models is an integral part and fundamental core element of the parametric approach.

We had tried many mechanical properties and tuned the model until we had reached plastic deformation and remnant displacement after deloading. The goal of this iteration is to reach calculable remaining deformation after removal of the force.

Methods

We had represented the current model utilizing concise mode of a single tooth as the representation of entire mandible could take several weeks to be complete. One of the models take about 3 days to be finished. This model hadn't represented the laminated structure of the bone. It demonstrates very simplified aspect of the biomechanical properties of the bone

Figure 4 These 2 models had been suggested to represent our model

This model had these elements.

- The tooth with dentine-like properties, we had neglected the effect of the enamel although in the dental trauma model we had considered it, but here we had not considered it.
- The bracket was modeled from ceramic.
- The PD ligament had been modeled as a soft layer.
- The bone had been arranged in concentric layers. These layers had been assigned to have the same mechanical properties. Nevertheless, it allows us to analyze each part carefully.
- Rods-like structures that extend from the tooth to the outer surface of the bone.

We had done 3 analyses with this model

- 1- First model as a reference where all material had pure elastic properties.
- 2- The bone had been assigned as material with elastoplastic properties and the rods had just elastic properties.
- 3- The previous had been reversed.

In both previous models, the force was 1N/m applied to the anterior surface of the bracket. The bone had been stabilized at the lower edges.

Results

Figure 5 Displacement of the totally elastic model

Figure 6 Displacement of the totally elastic model from another view

Figure 7 These elements had plastic properties, while hidden elements had elastic properties. The next elements had elastic properties, while hidden elements had plastic properties.

Figure 8 In order to get to the final stage, we had tuned the mechanical properties of the plastic material until we had gotten the plastic deformation. Although we think that plastic deformation of the bone is totally different from that of the engineering materials.

Figure 9 This is the response of the model with totally elastic properties

Figure 10 First trial of the plastic assignment

Figure 11 Same previous material but with higher load

Figure 12 same previous higher load but with material of less modulus of elasticity. The purpose of the current model is to demonstrate our model in an objective way

Figure 13 Same higher load, but softer material

Figure 14 Even softer material than in the previous example

Figure 15 This is the softest material with the same higher load. At this stage the plastic deformation starts to be revealed.

Figure 16 This is the remaining displacement after removal of the load in the previous experiment.

Figure 17 This model is for elastoplastic. Legend tuning is needed to demonstrate the comprehensible data. This is another iteration had been made by assigning the plastic mechanical properties to the rods radiating from the tooth model.

Figure 18 This model is for remaining displacement. The color changes had been significantly different. Accordingly, we had to modify the legend values.

Figure 19 In this model we had reversed the assignment of the materials to study other iterations. These iterations give great opportunity and make thinking out of the box.

Figure 20 The remaining displacement

Figure 21 Another model had been arranged to include the concentric region of the bone with successive repetition of plasticity and then elasticity

Figure 22 Remaining displacement of the previous model

Figure 23 the same previous model maximum displacement after he load

Figure 24 The last 2 models are with change legend that had been done to get better colors distributions. Digital models are highly modifiable and could be tuned to attain a parametric approach.

Conclusion

We had represented the current model utilizing concise mode of a single tooth as the representation of entire mandible could take several weeks to be finished

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.